

Environment and its influence

Physiological differences in rice desiccation and maturation

E. Alyoshin, N. Alyoshin, and E. Avakyan, Laboratory of Rice Physiology, Department of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry, Kuban Agricultural Institute, Kalinina 13, Krasnodar 350044, USSR

In the USSR, rice is harvested in a period of low temperatures and rains. Therefore, methods to accelerate maturation are being developed and tested. They are desiccation [MgCl_2 solution (0.01%) spray on fully ripened rice] and seniccation [mixture of 2,4-D (0.01%) and $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ (20%) or CO

$(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (20%) solutions on milky-wax ripened rice]. Both methods allow the initiation of harvest 7 days earlier, but the mechanisms differ. Desiccation destroys the cells' ability to hold water, drying and killing the plant's vegetative organs, but it does not change the yield or grain quality. When used to seniccate rice, 2,4-D makes the leaves permeable to inorganic nitrogen or phosphorus, activating the hydrolysis of protoplasmic matters and their movement into the grain (see figure).

Thus seniccation is the artificial accelerator of ripening, which becomes a forced process. Seniccation not only

Seniccation action on the rice leaf.

accelerates ripening, but also increases the yield by 0.3 t/ha (arithmetical mean obtained after 5 years of experiments on a total area of 3,500 ha) and improves grain quality. It increases the 1,000-grain mass and seed germination ability. Thus it is more effective than desiccation. We believe that seniccation followed by desiccation is most effective. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Management and performance of transplanted aus rice in a sample village in Bangladesh

M. Zahidul Hoque and Raisuddin Akanda, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

A monitoring study was conducted on the management and performance of farmers' 1979 aus crop in Salna village, Dacca District. Since the village has irrigation facilities, the major cropping pattern is boro rice-transplanted aman (T. aman) rice. However, some farmers grow local and modern varieties of aus rice in either rainfed or partially irrigated conditions in transplanted aus (T. aus)-T. aman, boro-T. aus, and boro-T. aus-T. aman cropping patterns. Only 12 farmers grew aus rice in the study area and monitoring was through daily record keeping in the fields. Yields were determined by sample crop cutting and expressed in kilograms per hectare at 14% moisture content. The cost and return values were calculated on the basis of actual day-today rates and pri-

Farmers' management practices, yield and returns for the local variety Pukhi and the modern varieties BRI (Chandina), BR3, and BR6 grown as transplanted aus rice in 1979 aus, Salna village, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Item	Aus rice	
	Local	Modern
Samples (%)	33	67
Plowings (av no.)	3	4
Plowings (range)	2-4	3-7
Laddering (av no.)	2	3
Laddering (range)	2-3	2-3
Date of transplanting (av)	19 Jun	12 May
Transplanting date (range)	16-19 Jun	25 Apr-13 May
Av seedling age (days)	27	35
Range of seedling age (days)	25-27	26-61
Farmers who used basal N (%)	100	100
Farmers who used topdressed N (%)	50	75
Av rate of N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O (kg/ha)	50-43-0	63-45-0
Farmers who used organic manure (kg/ha)	0	50
Av rate of organic manure (kg/ha)	0	4173
Farmers who irrigated (%)	0	63
Farmers who did not weed (%)	0	25
Farmers who weeded once (%)	25	0
Farmers who weeded twice (%)	75	75
Farmers who used pest control (%)	0	38
Av field duration (days)	70	88
Range of field duration (days)	65-72	75-105
Av yield (t/ha)	2.34	3.76
Range of yield (t/ha)	2.25-2.47	2.42-4.98
Av cost of production (\$/ha)	105.53	142.33
Range of cost of production (\$/ha)	90.07-115.87	91.60-165.66
Av net return (\$/ha)	458.00	845.27
Range of net return (\$/ha)	437.73-482.00	503.73-1163.73